

Solution of the Secular Equation in the Ninth Order Problem in Vinyl Halide

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The method of Isotani is extended to ninth order vibrational problem to calculate the force constant in the case of X_2Y_2Z (C_s) type molecules. The validity of the method is discussed in terms of the consistency of the diagonal force constants.

An attempt has been made for the first time to study the applicability of the method of Isotani¹ to higher order vibrational problems to compute the force constants in vinyl halide (C_2H_3Cl). The reasonability of the method consists in the consistent set of values obtained for the diagonal elements.

Any $n \times n$ vibrational problem contains n equations of degree from 1 to n involving $n(n+1)/2$ force constants. Isotani has given a method to determine the off-diagonal elements F_{ij} from the corresponding G_{ii} , G_{jj} , G_{ij} and λ_i elements only. Thus the ninth and third order problems involved in this type of molecule are reduced in turn to various second order ones by considering only the corresponding i and j modes. The F_{ij} elements obtained thus will give eight different values in the ninth order problem and two different values in third order problem. These diagonal elements agree very closely and hence their mean value is taken.

Theoretical considerations : The molecules taken up for study here are C_2H_3Cl belonging to the C_s point group with the frequency distribution of $9A'$ (in-plane vibration) and $3A''$ (out-of-plane vibration) modes. The symmetry coordinates and theoretical considerations for those molecules are the same as adopted earlier².

Results and Discussion

The structural parameters and vibrational frequencies are taken from EL-Sabbar and Zwolinski³. The F_{ij} values calculated by the method of Isotani by reducing to 36 different second order problems in A' species are listed in Table 1. It may be noted that the eight values for each diagonal element F_{ii} are close enough to justify the calculation of the mean value. The percentage of variation among the several values obtained for the same F_{ii} is very little.

TABLE 1 - SYMMETRISED FORCE CONSTANTS BY REDUCTION TO SECOND ORDER (mdyn/Å)

F_{11}	F_{22}	F_{33}	F_{44}	F_{55}	F_{66}	F_{77}	F_{88}	F_{99}	F_{ij}
9.33	5.26	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.56
9.27	-	5.12	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.71
9.15	-	-	2.90	-	-	-	-	-	0.32
9.24	-	-	-	5.24	-	-	-	-	0.55
9.11	-	-	-	-	0.07	-	-	-	0.00
9.93	-	-	-	-	-	0.37	-	-	0.55
9.66	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.48	-	-0.50
9.11	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.35	-0.12
-	5.23	5.13	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.02
-	5.21	-	2.97	-	-	-	-	-	-1.08
-	5.23	-	-	5.22	-	-	-	-	0.01
-	5.23	-	-	-	0.08	-	-	-	0.27
-	5.23	-	-	-	-	0.32	-	-	-0.16
-	5.24	-	-	-	-	-	0.46	-	-0.10
-	5.21	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.37	-0.25
-	-	5.11	2.98	-	-	-	-	-	-1.11
-	-	5.14	-	5.22	-	-	-	-	-0.01
-	-	5.14	-	-	0.08	-	-	-	-0.23
-	-	5.15	-	-	-	0.32	-	-	0.14
-	-	5.12	-	-	-	-	0.48	-	0.10
-	-	5.15	-	-	-	-	-	0.36	0.06
-	-	-	2.79	5.22	-	-	-	-	0.15
-	-	-	2.74	-	0.07	-	-	-	-0.03
-	-	-	3.04	-	-	0.32	-	-	-0.13
-	-	-	2.77	-	-	-	0.44	-	0.11
-	-	-	2.86	-	-	-	-	0.36	-0.14
-	-	-	-	5.24	0.07	-	-	-	-0.15
-	-	-	-	5.20	-	0.32	-	-	-0.18
-	-	-	-	5.19	-	-	0.45	-	-0.20
-	-	-	-	5.23	-	-	-	0.36	0.16
-	-	-	-	-	0.08	0.35	-	-	-0.13
-	-	-	-	-	0.07	-	0.44	-	-0.03
-	-	-	-	-	0.07	-	-	0.35	0.01
-	-	-	-	-	-	0.32	0.44	-	0.02
-	-	-	-	-	-	0.32	-	0.36	-0.03
-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.49	0.45	0.16
Mean values of F_{ii}									
9.35	5.23	5.13	2.88	5.22	0.07	0.33	0.46	0.37	-
Final converged values									
10.37	5.51	4.84	4.47	5.09	0.72	0.38	0.54	0.29	-

The mean values for F_{ii} (Table 1) when substituted in the secular equation along with the off-diagonal values satisfy secular equations to a

reasonable degree of approximation. To get perfect solutions from the secular equations, the off-diagonal elements may be fixed and the diagonal ones determined by the solution of the various non-linear equations obtained. This is a tedious process though it is possible. In such a case, these mean values of diagonal force constants may be used as initial sets of values for F_{ii} . This involves solution of non-linear equations using the Newton-Raphson method and the final converged values obtained thus are given in the last row of the Table 1. The observed and calculated frequencies are given in Table 2. This shows that there is

These values compare well with the values of 5.19 and 5.25 as reported by the same authors cited above^{3,4}.

The interaction force constants (F_{ij}) are relatively high for those involving the C=C symmetric stretching mode ($F_{1,2} = 0.56$, $F_{1,3} = 0.71$, $F_{1,5} = 0.55$, $F_{1,6} = -0.50$ mdyn/Å). In nearly half the number of cases interaction constants assume negative values. These negative interaction force constants normally yield positive compliance constants (inverse of force constants) in the corresponding positions and hence positive interaction coordinates

TABLE 2 - OBSERVED AND CALCULATED VALUES OF IN-PLANE FUNDAMENTAL WAVE NUMBERS OF VINYL CHLORIDE (cm⁻¹)

	C-C str.	CH ₂ sym. str.	CH ₂ Asym. str.	C-Cl str.	C-H str.	C-Cl defor.	C-H rock.	CH ₂ bend	CH ₂ rock
Observed	1 608.0	3 030.0	3 121.0	720.0	3 086.0	395.0	1 279.0	1 369.0	1 030.0
Calculated	1 608.2	3 028.0	3 124.0	721.0	3 089.0	396.0	1 283.0	1 372.0	1 027.9

good agreement between the observed and calculated values of wave numbers. The interaction force constants calculated as off-diagonal values and listed in the Table show the usual trend of low values when compared with the diagonal force constants except in two cases where they assume values greater than 1 mdyn/Å ($F_{2,4} = -1.08$ mdyn/Å and $F_{2,6} = -1.11$ mdyn/Å).

The C=C stretching force constant $F_{1,1}$ is 10.37 mdyn/Å which agrees with the value of 10.59 and 10.64 mdyn/Å as reported by Ramaswamy and Devarajan³ and Scherer and Overend⁴. The symmetrised force constant associated with the C-H symmetric stretching mode, $F_{2,2}$ and C-H asymmetric stretching mode, $F_{2,3}$ are nearly the same, the values respectively being 5.51 and 4.84 mdyn/Å.

which are the ratios of off-diagonal and on-diagonal compliance constants. This will lead to the explanation of the change in one of the two particular coordinates involved to be positive (or increase) while the other is slightly altered subject to the principle of minimisation of energy. The positive interaction force constants normally lead to negative interaction compliance constants correspondingly and the coordinates involved will decrease, for particular change in the other coordinate of the pair involved in the interaction term.

References

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